

Integrating various datasets to a common spatial scale: potential of Discrete Global Grid Systems (JHI-C2-1, WP1 T1.1)

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Executive summary

There is a need to improve how we integrate multiple spatial datasets for a range of modelling studies including GHG modelling. One potential way to integrate these various datasets to a common scale is to use a Discrete Global Grid System (DGGS). These divide the surface of the Earth into a tiling (tessellation) of cells, organized hierarchically in multiple resolutions. This brief report provides an overview of DGGSs, how they compare to existing GIS data models, the available DGGSs and how they are being explored used in research and in a wide range of commercial and public policy settings.

1. Introduction

In the, Scottish Government, Strategic Research Programme (SRP) Task 1.1 in the work package (JHI-C2-1) on 'Improving national GHG inventory', in year 2, I focussed on exploring ways to integrate various datasets to a common scale and how this could drive GHG models. GHG models require a range of input data related to soil, land, and climate information to be run. In this work package the GHG modelling work is to be carried out in Task 1.2 using the [DNDC](#) and [Ecosse](#) models. These spatial datasets come in a range of raster and vector formats, with different spatial resolutions. One potential way to integrate these various datasets to a common scale is to use a Discrete Global Grid System (DGGs).

Discrete Global Grid Systems (DGGs) divide the surface of the Earth into a tiling (tessellation) of cells, organized hierarchically in multi-resolution grids¹. Goodchild² reflecting in 2018 on how a modern approach to GIS would benefit from being based on globes rather than the 1960s map based approach that dominates today. He suggested that the multi-resolution nature of DGGs made them a good option for combining datasets with different spatial resolutions. Goodchild, went on to list the benefits of DGGs (quoted directly):

“First, there is no hiatus or break at the Poles or at 180 degrees longitude, as there is for cylindrical projections in Equatorial aspect, such as the Mercator or Plate Carrée. Second, the basic elements of a DGG at any level are approximately uniform in size and shape. Third, the spatial resolution of geographic information structured as a DGG is always explicit. This is in contrast to rasters, which inherit the distortions of the projection that was used to flatten the Earth so that a raster could be laid on it. Fourth, the use of a hierarchy based on powers of two lends itself well to the representation of data sets with varying spatial resolution. The quadtree has often been presented as a clever way of compressing geographic information, by using larger basic elements to represent areas of approximate uniformity, and smaller areas where there is greater variation. Fifth, the uniform resolution of a DGG could lend itself well to simulation of Earth-surface processes, and the solution of partial differential equations. Unlike finite-difference methods based on rasters, there are no boundary effects or variation in spatial resolution to deal with.”

Currently, single spatial resolution rectangularly gridded data is the basis of many modelling studies from local to national focussed assessments e.g. [UKCEH Land Cover Maps](#) available individually since LCM2020 as 10m, 25m, and 1km rasters. Traditional cartography (maps) is based on map projections, which are a function that relate points on the Earth's surface to points on a flat map. Where all map projections distort the underlying data in different ways.

Over the past six years, there has been increased growth in the use of DGGs, in part due to Google's open source release of their S2 library ([Google S2 blog post](#)) in 2017, and Uber's open sourcing their H3 (Hexagonal Hierarchical) Spatial Index ([Uber Engineering H3 blog post](#)). In the past year, H3 has been promoted heavily for large scale spatial analysis by leading cartographic companies like [Carto](#), [Foursquare](#), and [Kontur](#), as illustrated in this June 2023 Carto blog post on [Unlock the Potential of Spatial Indexes: 10 Powerful Uses of H3](#).

DGGs have been suggested to be a key component of Digital Earths³. There are an increasing range of learning resources related to DGGs (Appendix 1), as DGGs are integrated into a wide range of existing databases and geospatial tools (Appendix 2).

The [Open Geospatial Consortium](#) has been exploring how to support DGGs, and recently they completed [Testbed-16 innovation initiative](#) that included exploring the needs and key requirements for drafting an 'OGC Discrete Global Grid Systems (DGGs) Application Programming Interface (API) standard'.

2. Discrete Global Grid Systems

In this section a brief overview is provided of the more common DGGs.

2.1 H3 [main page](#)

H3 is a geospatial indexing system that partitions the world into hexagonal cells. It was written in C and there are bindings in a [range of languages](#) including Python, R, JavaScript, Go, and Rust. Hexagonal DGGs, like H3 are widely used for transportation e.g. Uber. Along with S2 they are the most widely used DGGs, for example companies like Carto and Foursquare make widespread use of H3. H3 has a couple of limitations, including the hexagons not being of equal area, which complicates spatial analysis, and they do not align simply with the current collection of raster-based earth observation data.

2.2 S2 [main page](#)

S2 is a library created by Google for spherical geometry i.e. representing all data on a three-dimensional sphere. There are libraries written in C++, Python, Go, and Java. One limitation of S2 is that it has a [complicated spatial index](#).

2.3 rHEALPix [paper](#)

The rHEALPix DGG is made up of a planar square grid and was described by Gibb⁴, who extended the existing HEALPix DGGs⁵, for geospatial applications - which had originally been developed for astronomer purposes. It has the advantage of having cells of equal area.

2.4 EASE-Grids [guide](#)

The Equal-Area Scalable Earth (EASE) Grids were created by the [National Snow and Ice Data Center](#) to be versatile formats for global-scale gridded data that uses an equal-area projection.

2.5 Icosahedral Snyder Equal Area Aperture 3 Hexagonal Grid (ISEA3H) [DGGRID v7 documentation](#)

Icosahedral Snyder Equal Area Aperture 3 Hexagonal Grid (ISEA3H) base polyhedron is the icosahedron, with its triangular faces partitioned into hexagons. Because each vertex of the

icosahedron is the meeting of 5 triangles, the grid shape at each vertex is necessarily a pentagon. Therefore, the grid contains 12 pentagons in total, regardless of the grid resolution, with area $5/6$ the area of the hexagons. 'Aperture 3' refers to the way in which refinements of the hexagons are performed, with the area of each hexagon decreasing by $1/3$ at each increasing resolution.

3. Discrete Global Grid System recent research and applications

There are an increasing number of research studies on comparisons between DGGs and traditional GIS, how DGGs differ, and on the application of DGGs to multi-scale assessments.

Li and Stefanakis⁶ carried out a comparison between DGGs and traditional GIS operations. The authors started by setting out the limitations of current GIS (which date back to the 1960s) in that information for a particular location is divided into multiple thematic layers. And that these layers often have a range of map projections in the creation of vector and raster data models, and the mapped features are primarily presented at a single level of resolution. In a move towards Digital Earth platforms, Goodchild *et al*⁷ highlighted the foundational role of DGGs. Hojati *et al*⁸ in their review of DGGs said "DGGs-based GIS could be the foundation of a computationally efficient, naturally multi-scale, and multi-stakeholder Digital Earth System, allowing for user-defined representations of diverse forms of geographical knowledge". The authors also highlighted a range of challenges and limitations including loss of information due to sets of cells compared to feature data models, and computational requirements of generating hierarchical datasets. Béjar *et al*⁸ recently demonstrated that a DGG based on the rHEALPix quadrangular cells could "be used to process raster datasets with current data cube technology, in this case Open Data Cube, without any changes to that software".

Mechenich and Žliobaitė⁹ recently created the Eco-ISEA3H database that comprised 17 spatial data sources including climate, landcover, and the geographic ranges of nearly 900 large mammalian species. They utilised the Icosahedral Snyder Equal Area (ISEA) aperture 3 hexagonal (3H) DGGs. A study by Li *et al*¹⁰ demonstrated the potential of Icosahedral Snyder Equal Area Aperture 3 Hexagonal Grid (ISEA3H) based data framework of 32 explanatory factors including biophysical and anthropogenic data to be integrated in a machine learning assessment of multi-scale flood mapping. These two studies demonstrated the potential of DGGs for providing an integrated data model for multi-scale assessments.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Key learning resources about Discrete Global Grid Systems

There are a growing range of DGGs learning resources. These include:

[CartoAcademy](#)

That includes an [Introduction to Spatial Indexes](#) where you can learn how to scale your analysis using DGGs.

YouTube resources

[SDSC23 Keynote | AI & H3: From adoption to integration | Javier de la Torre | CARTO Oct23 Spatial Data Science Conference](#)

Javier de la Torre, Founder and CSO at CARTO presented his keynote on the topic of Conversational GIS, and how we are enabling organizations to overcome the accessibility challenge of traditional GIS tools with Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI. This included the pivotal role of the H3 DGGs.

[2023 | Leveraging the Power of Uber H3 Indexing Library in Postgres for Geospatial Data Processing Aug23 FOSS4G](#)

This presentation demonstrates the use of Uber's H3 indexing library in Postgres for geospatial data processing through a series of examples and benchmarks. It will showcase the benefits of using Uber H3 indexing for geospatial data processing in Postgres, such as improved query performance and better partitioning of data.

Appendix 2. Integration of Discrete Global Grid System with existing databases and other tools

Despite the limitations of H3 hexagons not being of equal area, there are a wide range of databases and other tools have added support for H3:

PostgreSQL [h3-pg](#) PostgreSQL bindings for H3, a hierarchical hexagonal geospatial indexing system.

DuckDB [h3-duckdb](#) Bindings for H3 to DuckDB.

Xarray [xdggs](#) Xarray extension for DGGs supporting H3 and healpy.

[DGGs.jl](#) Discrete Global Grid System for Julia, based on [DGGRID](#).

ESRI

[Use H3 Hexagons for spatial analysis in ArcGIS Online](#) Jun23

[Use H3 to create multiresolution hexagon grids in ArcGIS Pro 3.1](#) Apr23

Sedona

[ST_H3CellDistance](#)

QGIS

[Geospatial Clustering with Uber's H3 in DuckDB & QGIS](#) Sep23

Snowflake

[Using GEOGRAPHY Objects With H3](#)

AWS Redshift

[Amazon Redshift announces support for H3 Indexing and related spatial grid indexing functions](#)

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